

1 **Xist control of ZMIZ2 and ZC3H12C.**

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7 The non-coding RNA Xist functions together with zinc finger nuclear factors in a large gene regulation
8 system known as the imprinting system. We describe here that the expression of two zinc finger nuclear
9 factors, ZMIZ2 and ZC3H12C, is controlled by Xist and that they likely operate with Xist in the imprinting
10 system that functions in regulation of gene expression through epigenetic mechanisms.

11 Citations

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